

DEVELOPMENT OF A PYROMETALLURGICAL METHOD FOR PROCESSING PERSISTENT GOLD-CONTAINING ORES AND PROCESSING PLANT WASTE

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Abstract. *The article discusses the key aspects of processing refractory ores and waste from beneficiation processes using pyrometallurgical methods. The focus is on the processes necessary for the effective extraction of precious metals from the slag during the smelting of the charge. The authors analyze modern recycling methods as well as technologies used to improve the quality of raw materials and increase the yield of precious metals. The study emphasizes the importance of optimizing preparatory processes to achieve maximum recycling efficiency and minimize resource losses.*

Keywords: *refractory ore, copper, charge, matte, slag, converter slag, extraction, clinker, concentrate.*

Introduction.

Located in the heart of Central Asia, Uzbekistan is one of the world's leading gold-producing countries. The republic ranks fifth in terms of proven gold reserves, and ninth in terms of production. These indicators highlight the importance of the gold mining industry for the country's economy and its strategic role in the international arena.

With an increase in global demand for non-ferrous metals, including gold, Uzbekistan is facing the need to adapt its mining industry to new conditions. Technological developments and increased consumption in various industries, such as electronics, construction, and jewelry, create additional opportunities to increase production and refining, depletion of rich and easily discovered ore deposits. Over the years of intensive mining, gold reserves in traditional deposits have begun to decline, which requires the search for new sources and the introduction of more efficient technologies. This contributes to the processing of persistent gold-bearing ores and waste from processing plants [1,2].

Currently, one of the most pressing problems is the choice of an effective technology for processing persistent sulfide ores and waste from processing plants. Pyrometallurgical processing of sulfide ores plays a key role in this issue.

We have investigated several sulfide deposits in Uzbekistan, including gold-silver-polymetallic ores in the antimony mineralization complex. In particular, we studied such deposits as Daugyztauskoye, Vysokovoltnoye, and Kokpatasskoye, which belong to the group of ore occurrences with gold-silver minerals and antimonite. Devanezay and Kaltazay fields in Navoi region, as well as Samarchuk, Kyzylalma and Kochbulak fields in Tashkent region were also studied. In these deposits, gold is represented as thinly interspersed in sulfides[3].

The study of the "Kyzylalma" ore deposit, which belongs to the moderate-sulfide type, revealed its outstanding diversity and complex composition. This deposit is located in the eastern part of the Beltau-Kurama volcanic-plutonic belt, in the Shavaz-Dukent graben. The length of the graben in the sublatitudinal direction reaches 40 km, with a width of 10-12 km. It is distinguished by its unique mineral composition, which includes more than 90 different ore minerals. The gold content in the ore of the Kyzylalma deposit [4] averages 4.88 cu, 25 cu. The main gold concentrators are quartz, pyrite, and iron hydroxides in the oxidation zone. Minor gold contents were observed in chalcocite, a product of chalcopyrite oxidation; nonmetallic minerals are represented by quartz, sericite, chlorite, kaolinite, and carbonate; thin aggregates of gold-bearing sulfides with sericite and chlorite can worsen the technological process.

Persistent carbon-arsenic ores of gold are complex in composition and structure of mineral raw materials, which makes them one of the most urgent and difficult problems for the gold mining industry at the world level.

In the research work carried out by NMMC specialists, it was found that the content of carbonaceous gold in the ores of the Kokpatas and Daugyztau deposits reaches 15% of the total volume. At the initial stage, the flotation concentrate oxidation process is carried out according to the biooxidation scheme, which makes it possible to effectively open sulfide gold. In this case, a significant part of the arsenic is dissolved and then converted to a solid form in the form of FeAsO_4 . Further, the biooxidation product with a low arsenic content is subjected to oxidative firing, which results in the release of gold bound to carbonaceous compounds. The resulting stub is sent for sorption cyanidation to extract gold. This method is very expensive. More than 75% of expenses are related to preparatory processes, which require a significant amount of water, especially in desert conditions [5].

Materials and methods

A pyrometallurgical method was developed for processing particularly hard ores of complex gold composition, such as the Kyzylalma deposit, which includes the use of gold — containing technogenic raw materials, namely clinker-technogenic waste from zinc production.

This process makes it possible to extract precious metals, which are then converted into mattes and transferred to copper production. The initial composition of the charge presented in Table 1 (sample 1-3) was prepared for these purposes.

Clinker obtained in the zinc production process of Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine (AGMK), which contained 3.2 g/t of gold (Au) and 260.7 g/t of silver (Ag), was used as a technogenic raw material for the extraction of non-ferrous precious metals. Sulfide copper concentrates produced at the AGMK copper processing plant were used for smelting to produce a sulfide matte (MOΦ). As a slag-forming flux, calcium oxide of the "ch" grade (CaO) was used, as well as converter slag from a copper smelter, which was characterized by a high content of silicon dioxide (SiO_2) – 23.35% and copper in the range of 2-5%.

The initial composition of the charge presented in Table 1 was prepared for these purposes. [6]

The experiment was performed for different ratios of components. In experiments No. 1 and No. 2, 8% MOF concentrate and 15% calcium oxide were added to the ore. In experiment No. 2, the percentage of ore in the composition was reduced (67%), but the conversion slag of the copper smelter was also added in the amount of 10%. In experiment No. 3, ore was 57%; MOF

concentrate, envelope slag and clinker of the Central Processing Plant were 10% each, and calcium oxide was 13%.

Table 1 - Chemical composition of the original feedstock

Raw material name	Cu	S	CaO	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	Zn	Au	Ag
	%							g / t	
Converter slag	2.70	1.61	1.00	23.35	46.74	2.52	1.23	2.6	18.2
Clinker	2.64	8.39	6.23	17.3	19.53	4.08	2.1	3.2	260.7
Concentrat MOF AGMK	16,56	23,52	1,02	24,06	18,92	2,74	-	1,8	64,7

Table 2-Charge compositions, smelting product yields, extraction of metals into matte

№ p/p _{t0}	Part of the charge	Weight of the charge		Output products	Weight products bottoms		Extract, %		
		g	%		g	%	metals	matte	slag, sublimates
1 1350 ⁰ C	Ore*	77	77	Stein	27	27	Copper	91,1	8,9
	Concentrate	8	8	Slag	58,6	58,6	Gold	97,2	2,8
	CaO	15	15	Sublimates	14,4	14,4	Silver	82,6	17,4
	Total	100	100	Total	100	100			
2 1400 ⁰ C	Ore*	67	67	matte	21,5	21,5	Copper	95,4	4,6
	Concentrate MOF	8	8	Slag	64,3	64,3	Gold	97,9	2,1
	Convery slag	10	10	Sublimates	14,2	14,2	Silver	92,5	7,5
	Sao	15	15						
	Total	100	100	Total	100	100			
3 1450 ⁰ C	Ore*	57	57	matte	18,0	18,0	Copper	97,6	2,4
	Concentrate MOF	10	10						
	Klinker CL	10	10	Slag	65,5	65,5	Gold	98,5	1,5
	Convery slag	10	10	Sublimates	16,5	16,5	Silver	97,1	2,9
	Sao	13	13						
	Total	100	100	Total	100	100			

Note: * Ore from the Kyzylalma deposit

Laboratory experiments were carried out according to the following methodology: an alund crucible was loaded with a load of charge (see Table 2) of various ratios, made up of three types of components, with a total weight of 100 g. The crucible was placed in an electric furnace of the Nabertherm brand, capable of reaching a maximum temperature of 1550°C. The samples were subjected to heat treatment for 2 hours after reaching the set temperature.

Based on the laboratory studies carried out in a given temperature range, it was found that the melting point of 1450 °C is optimal for achieving complete melting of the entire volume of the material and ensuring effective separation of melting products. At the same time, slags are

characterized by a low content of precious metals and copper, which indicates a high efficiency of the separation and purification process.

In the process of smelting metals from resistant ores of gold and gold-containing technogenic raw materials, the extraction efficiency in the form of mattes was 97.2–98.5% for gold, 80.6-97.1% for silver, and 91.1-97.6% for copper. These indicators show a high degree of recovery of valuable metals, which underlines the effectiveness of the processing technologies used.

Conclusion

A pyrometallurgical method is proposed, which involves the use of gold-containing technogenic raw materials, namely clinker-technogenic waste from zinc production and allows the extraction of precious metals, which are then converted into mattes and transferred to copper production.

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